

Proposal

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Submission date: 19-Oct-2025 08:43PM (UTC+0500)

Submission ID: 2785635423

File name: Research_Proposal.docx (42.65K)

Word count: 899

Character count: 5854

Research Proposal

AI-Based Thermal Analysis Framework for Penta Hybrid Nanofluids (PHNFs)

Problem Statement

The growing global need for efficient thermal management for electronic cooling, heavy industries, energy storage devices and biomedical applications have driven significant interest in hybrid nanofluids, due to its superior thermal exchange capabilities.

The present study focuses on developing Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based thermal analysis framework for Penta hybrid Nanofluids (PHNFs), those are composed of five distinct metallic and their oxides based nanoparticles dispersed in traditional base fluids. Nanoparticles are chosen based on their superior thermal conductivity thermal capacity.

However, the effective thermal characteristics of PHNFs is intricate, nonlinear and difficult to predict with traditional numerical and analytical techniques due to interparticle interactions, stability and thermophysical parameters.

This study aims to employ AI-based machine learning and Physics Informed Neural Network (PINNs) models, to predict precisely the thermal exchange behavior and flow. The outcomes will assist to design the next generation thermal management devices.

Hypothesis: AI-models can predict thermal characteristics and thermal exchange performances, accurately and precisely, when trained on experimental and simulated datasets of PHNFs, as compared to conventional correlations and regressions.

Objectives and Scope

To build AI-based framework for the prediction of flow rate and thermal exchange behavior of PHNFs for the use in effective thermal management systems and industrial use. To replace the traditional fluids with advanced modified species. A better thermal management can be beneficial for many evolving EV industry and electric locomotives.

1. Analyzing thermophysical characteristics in laminar and turbulent flow regimes.
2. Identifying ideal nanoparticles combinations and volume ratios for best thermal exchange efficiency.
3. Validation of model with numerical and experimental data.
4. Explore the applications of PHNFs in industries and large scale thermal management activities.

Research Significance and the Challenges Addressed

- A Novel hybrid AI or PINN-based model for PHNFs.
- Integration of deep learning + physics-informed constraints for accurate and interpretable predictions.
- Provides generalizable, domain-crossing applications of PHNFs in real-world energy and cooling systems.

(i) Research Questions

1. How AI-based algorithms optimizes the nonlinear thermal behaviour of PHNFs?
2. Which parameters influences most on PHNFs performance?
3. Does hybrid AI-framework provide required accuracy and precision?
4. How can these models contribute in applications of daily-world problems?

(ii) Literature Review

Nanofluids and Hybrid Nanofluids: Previous researches (Choi, 1995; Eastman et al., 2001) realized that nanofluids were better heat transfer fluids. Multi nanoparticles hybrid nanofluids exhibited better performance than mono nanofluids (Sajid & Ali, 2019).

Penta Hybrid Nanofluids: According to recent studies (Sundar et al., 2020; Esfe et al., 2022), PHNFs showed enhanced thermal conductivity and stability. Nevertheless, their properties are complicated by nonlinear interactions of multi-nanoparticles.

Nanofluid Research in AI: ANN, SVM, and deep learning models have been used to scheme nanofluid properties (Sharma et al., 2021; Alawi et al., 2022). The use of physics-informed neural networks (H. Qureshi et al., 2025) is promising with regard to the implementation of physical constraints to enhance generalization.

Gap: There is a lack of literature on the use of AI-based frameworks on PHNFs, even though their significance is increasing. The urgent requirement is to develop generalizable, interpretable, and correct predictive models of PHNF thermal analysis.

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Research Methodology

The methodology of the present research continues by following steps mentioned below.

1. Data Collection
 - Synthetic or experimental datasets of PHNFs (thermal conductivity, viscosity, heat capacity, density).
 - Simulation datasets (molecular dynamics and CFD for PHNF flows) using Python, Mathematica or ANSYS..
2. Feature Engineering
 - Nanoparticle types, sizes, shapes, and concentrations.
 - Base fluid properties (thermal conductivity, viscosity).
 - Operating conditions (temperature, Reynolds number, flow regime).
3. Model Development
 - AI algorithms: ANN, CNN, RNN, Transformer models.
 - Physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) for embedding energy conservation laws.
 - Selections of suitable hyperparameters, activation functions and optimizers, to train the neural networks model.
 - Hybrid ensemble models to improve robustness.
4. Model Training & Validation
 - Data split into training/validation/test sets.
 - Evaluation metrics: RMSE, R², MAPE.

- Comparison with empirical correlations and regression-based models.

5. Application Case Studies

- Electronics cooling (microchannel heat sinks).
- Solar thermal collectors.
- Biomedical heat transfer applications.

Flowchart

Model Training & Validation

Methodology

- Accuracy Evaluation
- Benchmarking with Classical Correlations

Application Case Studies

Real-world implementations

Electronics Cooling,
Renewable Energy,
Biomedical Systems

Contribution & Insights

Publications and seminars

Scalable AI Framework for PHNFs

Expected Outcomes

- Developing an effective AI-based algorithm for thermal analysis of PHNFs.
- Comprehensive description of nonlinear interactions of nanoparticles in the PHNFs.
- Advisory for experimental researchers and industries to select right combination of nanoparticles and PHNFs for right job.
- Support to high level thermal management sectors for adoption of best efficient species.
- Guidance for experimental researchers in selecting nanoparticle combinations for target applications.
- 3-4 Publications in international high impact factor journals and presenting paper in international conferences.
- Organizing conference and dissemination of research outcomes through modern available means.
- Industrial adoption support of PHNFs in energy-efficiency.

Proposal

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PRIMARY SOURCES

1	Muhammad Imran, Syed Tauseef Saeed, Jihad Younis, Imen Kebaili, Imed Boukhris, Ahmed Mir. "ANN-based thermal analysis of 3D MHD hybrid nanofluid flow over a shrinking sheet via LMA", Scientific Reports, 2025 Publication	2 %
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Nanoparticles Impact on Flow and Heat
Transfer of the Pulsatile Blood in Occluded
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Publication

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